

GENUS ALLIUM L. OF ALTAI MOUNTAIN COUNTRY

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Dataset on GBIF

Access to the dataset

Description

The dataset contains an up-to-date list of taxa of the genus *Allium* L. of Altai Mountain Country (<http://altaiflora.asu.ru>). The dataset is intended to provide all interested users of GBIF with information on the distribution of the genus within the AMC, identifying the locations of storage of material in world collections and other types of analyzes (taxonomic, phenological, etc.) using the available datasets in GBIF.

There is no taxonomic treatment of the genus *Allium* for the territory of AMC, only for whole Siberia (Friesen, 1987, 1988; Sinitsyna, 2019) or other regions included in the AMC – Mongolia (Friesen, 1995), China (Xu, Kamelin, 2000), Kazakhstan (Khasanov, 1996; Abdulina, 1998; Kotukhov, 2003). Our dataset contains an up-to-date list of the taxa of the genus in the AMC flora, considering recent information. The list of *Allium* species of AMC consists of 54 taxa including 2 subspecies.

Geographic scope

The database contains information on the distribution of the genus *Allium* L. of the Altai Mountain Country (AMC) within the territories of Russia, Mongolia, China and Kazakhstan.

Bibliography

1. Abdulina S.A. 1998. Checklist of vascular plants of Kazakhstan. 187 pp.
2. Friesen N. 1987. Allium L. In: L.I. Malyshev, G.A. Peshkova (eds.) Flora Sib. 4 (Araceae–Orchidaceae): 55–96.
3. Friesen N. 1988. Lukovye Sibiri: sistematika, kariologiya, khorologiya.
4. Friesen N. 1995. The genus Allium L. in the flora of Mongolia. Feddes Repertorium 106 (1–2): 59–81.
5. Friesen N., Fritsch R.M., Blattner F. R. 2006. Phylogeny and new intrageneric classification of Allium (Alliaceae) based on nuclear ribosomal DNA ITS sequences. Aliso 22: 372–395.
6. Khasanov F. O. 1996. Conspectus of the wild growing Allium species of Middle Asia. In: Ozturk, M., Secmen, O. and G. Gork (eds.) Plant life in the South-West and Central Asia. – EGE Univ. Press, Izmir: 141–159.
7. Kotukhov Ju. 2003. New species of the genus Allium L. (Alliaceae J. Agardh) from East Kazakhstan.
8. Sinitsyna T. A. 2019. Rod Allium L. (Alliaceae) Sibiri [Genus Allium L. (Alliaceae) of Siberia]. VAVILOVIA 2(3):3–22.
<https://doi.org/10.30901/2658-3860-2019-3-3-22>
9. Xu J.M., Kamelin R.V. 2000. Allium L. In: Wu Z.Y., Raven P.H. (eds.) Flora of China 24: 165–202.

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